

HIGHLIGHTS FOR NATURAL LAMINAR WING MANUFACTURING DEVELOPMENTS

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ABSTRACT:

Aernnova, together with Airbus as industrial leader, and partners ITAINNOVA, SERTEC among others, developed within Cleansky (CS) FP7 (EU 7th Framework Program), new manufacturing processes for BLADE (Breakthrough Laminar Aircraft Demonstrator Europe) Natural Laminar Flow (NLF) wings for an A340 Flight Test Bed. Then, within Cleansky 2 (CS2) H2020 (EU 8th Framework Program), further studies within LPA (Large Passenger Aircraft) in collaboration with Airbus, DLR and Onera are being performed as part of new Hybrid Laminar Flow Control (HLFC) ground structural and functional demonstrators.

This contribution provides a summary of CS manufacturing process to achieve laminar flow and current CS2 developments as state today. The key aspects of these studies are highlighted, together with the associated technology developments, in particular in relation to the new concepts and related manufacturing processes, and their numerical simulations, as key enablers to achieve laminar flow objectives.

1. INTRODUCTION

The aeronautical sector has been always characterized for continuous research and technology development efforts for more efficient aircrafts. The stable growth of the commercial air transport [1] is not compensated by the past

efficiency improvements rhythms, and requires additional efforts to comply with carbon neutral aviation goals by 2050 [2].

The commercial transport aircraft efficiency rests basically on three pillars: structural weight reductions, enhanced aerodynamics and improved engine specific consumption. The more efficient aerodynamics in cruise condition is translated into minimizing the drag, so the fuel burn and emissions. The studies and technology developments on wing laminar flow serve for this purpose, either natural laminar flow or hybrid laminar flow control with the suction of the boundary layer.

The Cleansky SFWA (Smart Fixed Wing Aircraft) BLADE project has completed a successful flight testing campaign on natural laminar flow wings. For this purpose the BLADE laminar requirements to the manufacturing processes of the wings were more challenging than a conventional turbulent development [3]. These tighter production tolerances affect the manufacturing parameters. The achievement of the final geometrical features values together with a lower level of uncertainty, are beyond conventional industrial set ups. The literature search performed for BLADE by Aernnova with the support of ITAINNOVA resulted on studies on accumulative tolerances and their influence in the manufacturing costs [4]. The assemblies have tighter tolerance requirements than those assumed under no deformations conditions during the assembly processes. Therefore interaction between parts as a consequence of the deviations generated by the tools or the assembly jigs, the distortions

generated in the joints, or the spring-back effects in the parts cannot be neglected. The development of structural deformation calculation techniques and the methods of tolerances accumulation is needed [5]–[7]. The elementary parts tolerances, the tooling for the assembly of the components, the sequence of riveting, the measurements integration into the assembly process, were numerically simulated and then developed on a flight demonstrator test bed. The CS NLF Wings assembly process consisted on well-defined operations, the most relevant are listed below:

- Positioning, parts located in assembly jigs
- Initial verification of clearances.
- Drilling in previous diameters + fixation through temporary fasteners.
- Application of shim + re-locate the parts in the tools + second fixation through temporary fasteners.
- Enlargement of holes up to the final diameters.
- Demounting, de-burring and clean.
- Application of sealant + re-locate the parts in the tools + third fixation through temporary fasteners.
- Riveting, final fastening.
- Geometrical measurements.

The assembly tooling for the left and right wings, see Fig.1, include one order of magnitude more reference hard points that those required more a conventional turbulent wing, i. e. ERJ- 145 wing required around 10 reference hard tooling assembly points. Fig. 2 and 3 depict the wings tooling and some of the assembly process steps to show the high number of reference hard tooling positioners.

Figure 1. RH and LH NLF Wings Tools for BLADE in Aernnova Berantevilla plant

Figure 2.NLF Wing Assembly step, front view

Figure 3.NLF Wing Assembly step, rear view

The CS2 LPA includes demonstrators for hybrid laminar flow control. The passive or active suction of the boundary layer is the key technology to achieve laminar flow. But, there is a need to maintain good tolerances management for natural laminar flow surfaces, joints, steps, gaps and waviness. This is the aim of this article, to highlight the manufacturing process related technologies that are directly linked with laminar flow demonstrators.

2. CS NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS FOR NLF ASSEMBLY REQUIREMENTS

ITAINNOVA and Aernnova developed together the studies and numerical simulations that enable the BLADE wings laminar assembly. The most relevant objectives and requirements of these studies were the following ones:

- To determine key driving parameters in the assembly processes.
- To determine how the deviations in the constituent components can affect to the final assembly tolerances.
- To determine if the deviations in the assembly jigs can produce significant

deviations in the final assembly tolerances.

- To analyse the influence of the type of fasteners, nuts, washers, and other joining elements
- To evaluate different assembly strategies and provide insights to the tools design and the assembly production processes. This includes the assembly process optimum sequence.

The initial studies conclude that the NLF Wings geometric tolerances values are in the same order of magnitude as the deformations generated during the assembly processes, which in consequence, cannot be dismissed. In particular the hypothesis of elementary parts behaving as rigid bodies during the assembly steps, that cannot be considered for NLF processes. As it could be anticipated, the assemblies' final tolerances are strongly affected by the elementary part initial compliances and the tooling fixed reference points uncertainties.

2.1. NLF Wings FEM Model, Key Data

It was required to develop a methodology to analyse the accumulation and propagation of deviations from the tools and the elementary parts to the assembly steps. It was decided to develop a Methodology based on the Finite Element Method (FEM) [8], [9], to cover, among others, the following key aspects:

- The definition of FEM strategies for the simulation of the assembly process.
- The cumulative analysis of tolerances based on FE calculations.
- The development of an application for the analysis of the results.

The FE simulation strategy was defined to take into account the assembly process proposed for the NLF Wings including among other simulations, the following ones:

- The fasteners joints, to include the in-plane strains produced locally, see Fig. 4
- The initial fixations induced forces through the temporary fasteners, clecos, selected for the NLF wings assembly, see Fig. 5. These forces were measured with a

dedicated test set-up and were found to be in the order of 1400 N.

- The application of shim and sealant and their influence on the local deformations, see Fig. 6

Figure 4. Fastener joint FEM and test set-up

Figure 5. Cleco and its FEM simulation

Figure 6. Shim and sealant substrates FEM simulation

The complete FEM model included the following key features:

- The assembly jig cradles for the Upper Cover and the Leading Edge, and the supports for the positioning/fixation of the Front Spar and the Rear Spar, with connectors to represent the fixation elements, see Fig. 7. Also the connectors for the positioning and guiding of the rest of parts. The Fig. 7 depicts the fixations of the main parts representing the assembly jig, cradles and support structures for FS and RS; the corresponding FEM nodes have all degrees of freedom constrained. Also the fixations of the connector

elements used for the positioning and guiding of the rest of parts, Ribs and the Lower Covers are depicted.

- The elementary parts detailed models: Upper Cover, Leading Edge, Front Spar, Rear Spar, Ribs and the Front, Central and Rear Lower Covers, see Fig. 8
- The fasteners, bolts and temporary fasteners FEM features, including shim and sealant, see Fig. 9

Figure 7. NLF Wings FEM: assembly, tool main cradles, spars supports and fixation points details.

Figure 8. NLF Wings FEM: detail showing the different elementary parts

Figure 9. NLF Wings FEM: fasteners and clecos details.

2.2. NLF Wings FEM Model, Loads

The FEM model was loaded under different scenarios to obtain sensitivity effects on the NLF final assembly tolerances. These loads come from the in- built assembly forces induced by the fixation points on the tool, the forces introduced by the fastening operations and the gravity.

The initial studies focused on the sensitivities of the loading originated by the elementary parts deformations and so induced deviations in the fixation points. The assessment on what deviations might be presented in the different elementary parts, are based on studies that account for the materials and manufacturing process, the size of the parts and their shapes.

The NLF Wings consist on a hybrid composite-metal structure. The upper cover and leading edge are composite and the lower covers, spars and ribs are metallic.

The metallic elements are machined aluminium components that for the sizes of the parts can achieve deviations in the order of 1 mm. But, due to the possibility of applying finishes processes like shot peening, the final deviations can be below 0.5 mm or slenderness elements like the spars sizes 10 m by 0.3 m; and for stiffened panels like the covers- 10 m by 1 m typ. - the maximum deviation below 0.25 mm. The metallic ribs can be considered with negligible deviations.

The composite parts present a symmetric and balanced lay up to avoid deformation- loading couplings. The loads to be considered are not only mechanical forces, but temperature and hygroscopic ones. This state of the art practice is extended and it needs to be fulfil in strict

tolerances production like BLADE, to minimize the undesirable spring back effects while curing.

The symmetric laminates are characterised by mirror stacking sequence of the lay ups with respect to the laminate mid plane. The balanced laminates consist on the existence of the same number of plies with positive and negative ply orientation $\pm \theta$

The Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) [10] provides the composite laminate stiffness properties that are mechanically characterized by three stiffness matrix: the membrane matrix [A], the bending matrix [D], and the coupling matrix [B]

The balanced laminates presents no tension-shear and no bending-twist coupling which results in $\langle A_{13} \rangle = \langle A_{23} \rangle = 0$ and $\langle D_{13} \rangle = \langle D_{23} \rangle = 0$. The symmetric laminates coupling matrix is zero, $[B] = 0$ that results on no membrane-bending coupling.

The composite manufacturing processes are not as robust as the aluminium metallic machine. For the upper cover size 10 m by 2 m the standard deviations can be as big as 0.05% but due to the demonstrator special character of the BLADE, the strict than usual tolerances management on elementary composites parts production, less than half this deviation can be achieved in flatness.

It was concluded the need to characterize 7 different initial Unitary Load Cases (ULC) based on deviations of the elementary parts:

- Upper Cover – Spring Back (UCSB) consisting on a 1 mm maximum deflection at the rear spar location, Fig. 10
- Upper Cover – Rib-Foot (UCRF) that accounts for 2 mm deviation in the position of one of the rib feet. It was selected rib 9. The deviation introduced directly through a displacement of the nodes associated to the rib-feet, Fig. 11.
- Front Spar and Rear Spar (FS5B and RS5B, two different ULC) approximately a 0.5 mm bending induced deviation in both extremes, Fig. 12
- Front, Central and Rear lower covers (FC25, CC25, RC25; 3 different ULC) with 0.25 mm of deviation of the parts

representing torsional deformation, Fig. 13

Figure 10. Upper Cover Spring Back loading.

Figure 11. Rib 9 Rib Feet deviation loading.

Figure 12. Front Spar bending deviation loading.

Figure 13. Central Lower Cover twist deviation loading

Then, the load cases have been defined as combinations of these individual deviations, ULC, following an orthogonal array L8: Seven two-level factors (1: without deviation, 2: with deviation), which may allow later to perform an analysis of effects and influences following a Robust Design Method [11], Tab. 1.

	UCSB	UCRF	FS5B	RS5B	FC25	CC25	RC25
LC1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
LC2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1
LC3	2	2	1	1	1	2	2
LC4	1	1	2	2	1	2	2
LC5	2	1	1	2	2	1	2
LC6	1	2	2	1	2	1	2
LC7	1	2	1	2	2	2	1
LC8	2	1	2	1	2	2	1

Table 1. NLF Wing Assembly FEM load cases

2.3. NLF Wings FEM Model, Results

The FEM model converged properly and provided results in 7 out of the 8 load conditions. The exception was case number 4, that due to reasons, pending studies, did not converge.

There were different results analysed but one of the key ones, is about the upper skin waviness after the assembly processes simulations. The analysis of the waviness is based on the calculation of the 'b/a' ratios and 'b' along the surface, Fig. 14.

Figure 14. Waviness parameters "a", "b"

The FEM model results were post-processed for the 7 converging load cases. It was obtained the upper skin waviness results in different chord-wise sections. It was found that the most critical sections were section 53 and 57, both in the adjacent area of rib 9, and mainly due to the cumulative effects of deviations from the loading cases in that particular region.

The case 3 and the section C53 waviness are depicted, Fig. 15, with the corresponding "b/a" and "b" critical waviness values

Figure 15. Post-processing results, load case 3

The key result came from the analysis of the effect of the individual deviations into the waviness. For this purpose, the orthogonal arrays enabled the analysis of the influence of the different deviations factors under study, on the final upper surface waviness. This means to determine which factors or deviations are the most important in terms of the response being analysed. The waviness parameters, maximum "b" value and "b/a" were the responses to analyse. The weight factors on both key parameters were obtained, Tab. 2.

	% influence "b"	% influence "b/a"
UCSB	89,7	3,6
UCRF	4,2	91,9
FS5B	0,0	0,2
RS5B	0,1	0,2
FC25	5,8	3,8
CC25	0,1	0,1
RC25	0,0	0,3

Table 2. Waviness Weight Factors of the ULC

These results evidence that, among the deviations analysed, the deviations considered for the Upper Covers are the most critical ones. The control of the geometry of the composite Upper Cover and its positioning in the jig tool is the most critical assembly process step.

These results confirm that the deviations defined for the Front Spar, Rear Spar, and the Lower Covers, for the magnitudes established as representative for aluminium machined parts, have a lower influence in the waviness of the Upper Cover surface.

3. SEALANT APPLICATIONS AND ITS EFFECT ON GAPS AND STEPS

The sealant application is demanded to fill gaps and achieve surface finishes for laminar flow. The most relevant requirements for the sealants are:

- They must show good adhesion properties to the substrates
- They have to be applicable within adequate process time, to the different steps and gaps geometries.
- The recovered surface of the sealed gap must be within very restrictive geometrical tolerances, typically below 100 μm

Aernnova Technology Development teams are studying, developing and testing several types of new seals. These are provided by different collaborations. The results obtained have not been completed yet. There are ongoing efforts to study sealants on over-countersunk fastener joints, in Line of Flight (iLoF) and across the Line of Flight (aLoF) according to Airbus standards. These standards are quite extensive and include, on top of the technical specifications of sealants, the preparation of holes in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) and hybrid joints (CFRP/Metal), the assemblies for fastening, the holes geometries for use with protruding and countersunk head fasteners and specific nuts and the torque tightening of screws, bolts and nuts.

Based on all current best practices, a new definition of requirements for the sealant properties has been established for the new CS2 HLFC Wing geometries and mechanical behaviour in flight. The Wing surface quality requirements needs to be fully characterized up front. These studies are concluded with the pre-selection of sealants candidates.

Then for each one of the sealants, detailed studies are being performed for each of the most relevant geometrical features. These analysis include the development of adequate measurement techniques for the gaps and steps geometries, previous and after the sealant application. These studies are validated with manufacturing trials and tests. The digital gauge clock has been chosen for the measurement and evaluation of the steps height.

Chemical and thermal sealant shrinkage behaviour has been studied. Then these studies have been validated with manufacturing coupons for different gaps geometries.

The actual measurement of the geometrical features needs to be within a tight tolerances range. For this purpose the Mercury Volume Dilatometer has been selected. These selected representative specimen gaps were sealed with different sealants and then measured at room temperature, 90°C and minus 50°C.

It has been concluded that the chemical shrinkage of the sealants is a very important topic to be considered, characterized and measured for next technology maturation steps. In particular, the best practice is to minimize the sealant material applied volume to avoid high chemical and thermal shrinkages.

The adhesion mechanical behaviour of the sealants has been also tested on the different substrate materials. This is an important step before further ground and flight testing, mainly because of the multi- material joining Aluminium, Titanium and CFRP. The thermal expansion coefficients of the sealants have been characterized by thermo-mechanical analysis.

The sealant application procedure for ground and flight testing is going to be based on a combination of manual application by spatula and wet grinding.

This previously described sealant application and measurement process was tested on the different substrate materials with the relevant geometrical features for anticipated 1 g cruise conditions gaps. As a result, for all these selected geometries it was possible to achieve step and gap heights below 50 μm according to the measurements done with a digital gauge clock and flat gauge, Fig. 16.

The application of "several" layers to reduce the chemical shrinkage effect was tested and measured in between applications (after curing).

Figure 16. Digital gauge clock and flat gauge (Mitutoyo)

4. CS2 HLFC LEADING EDGE- MAIN TORSION BOX INTERFACE

The laminar flow surface requirements are of particular relevance for the interface between the hybrid laminar flow leading edge and the wing main torsion box. The chord position of this interface is critical for the aerodynamics instabilities initiation and the surface quality needs to be as smooth as possible.

This interface is stressed by leading edge aerodynamic loads and the compatibility induced strains by the wing bending and torsion deformations. Therefore, the technical challenge is not only to achieve the laminar tolerances at aircraft on ground condition, but also for 1g cruise one.

The maintenance operations also require easy and fast dismountability of the Leading Edge (LE) from the Torsion Box (TB). The in service experience conclude on the need to achieve this requirement. There are different approaches to fulfil this need but the best compromise solution has to account with the laminar flow goals. This is a key subject of study, development and critical feature for the CS2 LPA HLFC demonstrators.

For one of these demonstrator a natural laminar joint is being developed. The concept is based on an innovative "Supplement- Adaptor" part, see Fig. 17. This option enables that the permanent

structural fasteners can be flush and there is a better control of the LE- TB gap to reach a small and controlled sealant bead. The sealant application is needed to recover laminar surface requirements in some critical spots.

Figure 17. Supplement- Adaptor part, concept scheme

This concept also respect current interfaces with an existing TB structure, no fastener position is lost and the same load transfer paths can be maintained. There is an easy conversion from current flying aircraft to HLFC by installing these adaptors.

The easy in service requirements have been translated into Interchangeability (ICY) ones. This means that the replacement in field of one HLFC LE by another one is achieved by ensuring exactly the same mechanical interface points, fasteners positions, etc. In order to fulfil this requirement several studies are being performed. One of them consists on Digital Mock Up (DMU) studies for an ICY simulation models and studies, Fig. 18

Figure 18. ICY models DMU simulation

This easy maintenance concept requires future Control Jigs and Interchangeability tools. The trend for more automation in airframe parts production will then need to be considered and new development are expected to cope with both requirements.

The studies on tolerance analysis for the different HLFC demonstrators are based on previous experience on similar structures. Aernnova counts with data for the Embraer- 145 Wing production. The key features of this wing production are available. This is complemented with the A350 Horizontal Tail Plane Leading Edge and parts tolerance analysis that is now in production.

Then the HLFC specifics must be considered. This includes the aerodynamics requirements for surface steps and gaps across Line of Flight (LOF) forward and backwards facing. Also the surface waviness for different amplitude ranges.

There is also a need to demonstrate the manufacturing capabilities for the elementary parts and assembly. This is based on studies that account for the design principles at the same level as the manufacturing process in relation to final part tolerances. The specific geometrical features and constraints have to be considered

5. CONCLUSIONS

The wings laminar flow objectives require very tight tolerances and smooth surface qualities, not only for Natural Laminar Flow wings, but also for Hybrid Laminar Flow Control solutions. The achievement of such tolerances are enabled by new material and manufacturing processes that can be numerically simulated.

During Cleansky SFWA project a new methodology to study the assembly processes in terms of deviations and tolerances was developed and experimentally validated for an aircraft wing torsion box. This methodology enable the a priori analysis of deviations that may arise during assembly processes caused by deviations in the constituent parts, deviations in the assembly jigs and other effects associated to the assembly operations itself. Then the assembly processes steps and the assembly jigs can be improved. These production processes were much handcrafted, far from a serial manufacturing industrial standard. The assembly hard tooling was a key element on achieving final tolerances, together with the simulation means.

The CS2 current efforts on HLFC include further studies on NLF. The need to industrialize the natural laminar joint Leading Edge- Wing Torsion Box in a much more efficient manner than in CS

project is one of the objectives. There are new solutions under investigation that are showing promising results.

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